

ISic0412

I.Sicily inscription 0412

Language

Latin

Type

building (?)

Material

stone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy**Last Change**

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 300 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : mm

Text

1. Syracusae colonia Augusta

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491644

EDCS 21900474

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7132 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/>)

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